

USE OF ICT IN UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the current state of the application of information and communication technologies to the educational process.*

Keywords: *information and communication technologies (ICT); educational process.*

Абстракт. *В статье анализируется современное состояние применения информационно-коммуникационных технологий в образовательном процессе.*

Ключевые слова: *информационно-коммуникационные технологии (ИКТ); учебный процесс.*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada o'quv jarayoniga axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarini qo'llashning hozirgi holati tahlil qilinadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari (AKT); ta'lim jarayoni.*

One of the main tasks of increasing the competitiveness and efficiency of an educational institution's educational process and research activities is the development and widespread introduction of information and communication technologies (ICT) [1, 2]. In addition to scientific and educational services used in the educational process, introducing a new network of practical services covering all areas of activity of an educational institution is conceptually important [3, 4]. These services include:

- a service for connecting to a single cable and wireless (Wi-Fi) network, allowing any employee, student, or graduate student to access information resources under their authority;
- service for conducting trainings and other public events (conferences, seminars, etc.) in a geographically distributed audience in multipoint video conferencing mode;

- IP telephony service for internal audio and video communication, multipoint conferencing service based on IP video telephony, and multipoint video conferencing tools;
- single-user authorization service for remote use of resources and some practical services of an educational institution (for example, a service for using library collections, including user registration and organizing access to the electronic resource system);
- maintenance of access in strict accordance with the powers of persons providing access to an educational institution's internal information resources and information databases;
- many other network applications.

The introduction of ICT in educational institutions ensures the following:

- widespread use of global Internet resources;
- operation of automation systems for library and management activities in an educational institution;
- use of software for educational purposes based on multimedia technologies.

Main areas of application of ICT:

1. Organization of an information service of an educational institution and its activities.
2. The use of video conferences in the educational process to cover scientific, cultural, and other events held in an educational institution.
3. The use of web technologies in all areas of activity of an educational institution.

This allows you to solve the following problems:

- formation and development of intellectual and creative abilities of promising youth;
- carries out training of professional personnel;
- formation of a conscious choice of future profession;
- improve the qualifications of teachers in the field of modern information technologies;
- creation of a vocational school to train young specialists with extensive knowledge and skills in the field of computer technology;

- creation of interactive educational materials that allow the use of the most modern multimedia technologies in the educational process, raising both teaching and self-study of students in the electronic library to a higher level.

Information and reference service. The information and reference service of an educational institution was created to promptly deliver the necessary information to all employees and students and provide the opportunity to receive reference information online in real-time [5, 6]. Methods of providing information:

- ✓ via touchscreen information kiosks upon request;
- ✓ replay on information panels.

In addition, a large amount of information, including educational and methodological materials, can be posted on the portal (website) of an educational institution.

Touch information kiosk. A touch information kiosk is a device equipped with a specialized computer and a vandal-proof touch display, designed to display information at the user's interactive request [6]. It is advisable to place information in the kiosk in the following order:

- presentation of the educational institution;
- Timetable of classes;
- video broadcast schedule.

In addition, when organizing free Wi-Fi zones, magnetic card readers or bill acceptors can be installed in kiosks. This allows you to pay for services provided through an electronic payment system.

Information panels. Bulletin boards are designed for cyclical repetition of advertising and reference materials. For example, advertising an educational institution, birthday greetings, various announcements, etc.

Free Internet access points. Currently, the creation and development of a unified information space is of great importance. The ongoing work to distribute Internet access services plays an important role.

Public Internet access point. A universal Internet access point (UIAP) is designed to provide users with access to the Internet and/or work with a computer in offline mode. This device is a software and hardware complex designed to provide users with access to the Internet and/or work with a computer in offline mode. Has the ability to prohibit (or limit) user access to certain Internet resources.

Organization of Wi-Fi zones. Wireless Internet connection via Wi-Fi is a modern and popular service. Wi-Fi devices are replacing traditional cable networks where cable infrastructure cannot be built. A Wi-Fi router allows you to organize computer access to the Internet, protecting them from attacks by intruders.

Use of video conferencing. Currently, the Russian company Video Port has developed video conferencing software that runs on personal computers running the Windows operating system. The Video Port system provides several operating modes. The most interesting mode is 2x120, in which up to 120 people can see and hear one or two speakers. If desired, the main participant can invite any other participating user to the discussion. Computer learning technologies allow you to more actively participate in the multifaceted process of exchanging information resources for the successful management of information flows.

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